

"That's not what they said": Verbal Misalignment in Subtitle Processing and its Effects on Cognitive Load

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Abstract. Subtitles are a useful tool for translating media and aiding in learning and accessibility, but the use of auto-generation software means that often subtitles are not accurate to what was actually said in videos. This current work builds on existing research on how the brain processes subtitles by investigating the effects of lexical errors on cognitive load. Using data collected in an eye tracking experiment, it was investigated how viewers distribute their attention when there is misalignment between the different forms of sensory input. The results show that lexical errors caused a significant increase in cognitive load (measured by fixation duration), which suggests that errors impact the consolidation of subtitle information. Along with this, lexical errors caused viewers to change their viewing behaviour patterns such as revisiting subtitle areas or not reading certain subtitles. It was also found that there is an effect of time on fixation count, dwell time, and the viewing behaviours which requires further investigation.

Keywords: subtitle processing; cognition; cognitive load; eye tracking

1 Introduction

During the COVID-19 pandemic, people were online more than ever before. Whether it was watching television, working from home, or attending classes online, people were existing in an increased number of digital spaces. This change caused many people to become aware of how different consuming digital content is to in-person interactions. An interesting facet of consuming digital content is how it has multiple streams of input people receive simultaneously. This information can include spoken language, visual imagery, written language, and other auditory components such as music. While all of these can be experienced in in-person environments, digital content usually has all the streams of input coming from a single source.

Such differences raise questions about how the brain copes with these multiple streams of information simultaneously. One example of these simultaneous streams of input is the presence of audio and textual input in videos with subtitles. Subtitles, sometimes called captions, are any form of written text which appears overtop a primarily visual piece of media such as movies, YouTube videos, or online lectures. People consume subtitles in a variety of forms, whether subtitles are translating the dialogue into another language (inter-lingual), transcribing the dialogue spoken in the same language (intra-lingual), or supplying additional information to the audience about the situation in the film (auxiliary). In terms of multisensory information, intra-lingual subtitles are interesting because they are presenting the same linguistic information¹ in two different types of input: audio-verbal and audio-visual/textual. Subtitles in general add an additional level of information which viewers have to process,

¹ Because of the natures of textual and verbal communication, they cannot truly communicate information identically. Most text lacks the ability to communicate specific acoustic information such as volume, timing, and other features like tone. There are some ways to represent these orthographically (such as punctuation for pauses) but strategies for this can vary (Sun & Wang, 2019). Here the word 'same' is because the text is the equivalent written form of what is spoken, so its meaning is based directly off the spoken phrase.

thereby raising the question of what processing strategies comprehenders rely on when integrating information in two forms no matter the type of subtitle, one of the major issues with subtitling is the amount of time and resources they take to write (Orrego-Carmona, 2016). Whether it is inter- or intralingual, subtitles are generally considered most accurate when written by a professional. This becomes a problem because many smaller forms of media do not have the resources to be able to produce high quality subtitles. Along with this, smaller language communities are less likely to receive professionally subtitled media in their language. To solve this, there have been efforts for audiences to generate their own subtitles (as investigated by Orrego-Carmona (2016)) or have them be automatically generated by different software. Both of these options are widely used, but both are known to have many potential inaccuracies. In the case of audience generated subtitles, problems include mistakes which are not caught in editing or limited proficiency in the original language for interlingual subtitles. Auto-generated subtitles work based on speech-to-text software which detect which words are being spoken are being spoken and which depend on large amounts of data for training. These are known to have issues with any non-standard accent or vocabulary, although such problems vary by how the software was designed and trained.

Along with word recognition issues, any additional auditory information may interfere with the software, so music and sound effects can make the software's guesses less accurate. Despite these inaccuracies, the subtitles are still used because they are helpful or necessary, especially for people who need interlingual subtitles or intralingual for accessibility concerns, such as d/Deafness or processing difficulties.

Since subtitles are generally meant to aid in processing or accessibility, making them as clear as possible is a major goal. Subtitles already act as an additional source of input alongside the audio stream, so minimizing the processing power needed is a major part of making the subtitles effective. One potential issue to effective subtitle processing is when subtitles are not accurate to the dialogue. Comprehenders generally understand that subtitles should have the same information in both the auditory and textual mediums, which would not be true in the case of inaccurate subtitles. Because the information does not match their expectations, it is possible that the processing effort would be increased by the audio-textual misalignment. Considering people are still using these inaccurate subtitles, it is possible that people are developing strategies for how they view the media in order to not experience overload. In other words, they could be adapting their viewing behaviours, such as using some form of information recovery strategies, or even not reading the inaccurate subtitles.

Before these recovery strategies can be assumed and investigated, it must first be shown that inaccurate subtitles are having an effect on media processing in the first place. Currently there is very little research which has looked into how people manage conflicting information which they expect to align, so it is not clear that inaccurate subtitles impact cognitive load. This current study will investigate the effects of inaccurate subtitles on viewer's cognitive processing and viewing behaviours to see if there is a noticeable difference between contexts with accurate versus inaccurate subtitles. If inaccurate subtitles are impacting cognitive load this will then open up possible research into the behavioural changes of viewers facing misaligned information. The findings show that viewers do experience increased cognitive load in response to inaccurate subtitles, suggesting that more research is needed on viewers' behavioural responses.

2 Literature Review

The current project has been developed from a strong history of research on subtitles and cognitive processing. This section will first discuss major areas of subtitle research and how they have varied. Following from that section, cognitive load will be discussed as one of the primary factors investigated

in subtitle research. Since this is often done through eye tracking studies, eye tracking as a methodology will then be discussed, with a focus on how eye tracking is used to measure cognitive load. Because of the multi-sensory nature of subtitled content, multimodal integration will then be discussed. Finally multimodal misalignment in subtitles will be explored, as there is currently a lack of work in this area describing the effects of lexical errors in subtitle processing.

2.1 Subtitles

Over the past few decades, subtitle research has generally fallen into a few major categories: subtitles in translation, subtitles in the classroom, subtitles for accessibility, and how subtitles can be optimised for comprehension or reduced cognitive load. Each of these areas has a largely different goal in mind, with the exception of optimisation, but they tend to look at similar features such as content comprehension, attention distribution, and cognitive load. At this time no research on auxiliary subtitles has been found, though it is possible that it may have been investigated within a media studies lens.

Inter-lingual subtitles for translating foreign media are one of the most common types people encounter, given that they make media from other cultures and in other languages more widely accessible. While lots of media also undergoes dubbing, the process of replacing the dialogue with localized audio, subtitles are still often a more accessible and less labour-intensive practice (Perego et al., 2016). Inter-lingual subtitles are also occasionally created through community generation instead of by large media companies. These community practices usually involve people who are bilingual taking the time to translate programs in order to make them available where they previously were not (Orrego-Carmona, 2016). This can happen with larger media which is not professionally translated for smaller language communities or occur on smaller form content such as YouTube videos, which allows limited community subtitle generation. Research on inter-lingual subtitles spans topics related to cognitive processing (Perego et al. 2016), differences between professional and amateur subtitles (Orego et al), and bilingual subtitles (subtitles both in their original language and a translation) (Liao, Kruger, and Doherty, 2020). All of these studies analyse cognitive load and comprehension of the subtitles, with the general finding that subtitles increased comprehension and did not increase cognitive load, even in the case of bilingual subtitles. The lack of increased cognitive load from bilingual subtitles is interesting because it suggests that the additional information stream from the subtitles does not necessarily interfere with other elements of processing, suggesting it may be due to viewers prioritising the language they are familiar with over the auditory information which is unfamiliar (Liao, Kruger, and Doherty, 2020). This pattern was noted particularly in inter-lingual subtitles in classroom settings, where the primary language of instruction was found to be prioritised even over students' native language (Kruger, 2013).

Subtitles in classroom settings are more often intra-lingual and the research on them usually has a strong focus on content comprehension and attention. Generally, the studies look at the usefulness of subtitles as a tool which can be added to video recordings and virtual lectures, though some research has also been done on how pre-existing subtitled media can be used for increasing student literacy (Goldman & Goldman, 1988). When looking at comprehension, multiple studies have found a significant increase in comprehension rates when subtitles are employed (Kalyuga, 2012; Kruger, 2013; Yoon & Kim, 2011). This is usually measured by comparing test scores of students who were exposed to subtitled classroom content and those who were not. In terms of how attention is allocated on screens, it has been found that subtitles lead to an increase in students' attention to non-subtitle areas which likely also contributes to the increase in comprehension. Classroom research has also been a primary area where subtitle optimisation has been relevant, specifically with the aim of helping students retain as much

information as possible. Research in this area does tend to make the assumption that subtitles are accurate, which leaves open a question of how these findings are impacted by subtitle inaccuracies.

Subtitles as a tool for accessibility are an interesting area because they exist between classroom use and translation. Most of the research in this vein focuses on Deaf and hard of hearing individuals because of the issue presented by largely auditory dialogue. For many Deaf individuals their first language is a Sign language, so they may have lower proficiency in the spoken language of their larger community, even in its written form. This means not only that subtitles need to be present to make media accessible, but also issues of clarity and style for optimised comprehension are pertinent. Research in this area thus has similar focuses on comprehension and attention like the previous two categories (Yoon & Kim, 2011) but also examines what styles of subtitles are most useful. For instance, Szarkowska et al. (2011) looked at how verbatim, edited, or standard subtitle types affected hearing, hard of hearing, and Deaf viewers differently. They found that overall, all groups had higher dwell time on verbatim subtitles, with Deaf participants spending more time than the other two groups on verbatim subtitles. Because higher dwell time is linked with increased cognitive, this means Deaf participants' processing is more impacted by verbatim subtitles than their hearing and hard of hearing counterparts. The significant difference of verbatim subtitles is likely because verbatim subtitles contain disfluencies and repairs which would make them less grammatical when written. These findings suggest that the less grammatical form of verbatim subtitles does increase the processing effort for people less accustomed to the grammatical errors of spoken speech, such as d/Deaf individuals. These findings show that less grammatical styles of subtitles (in this case verbatim subtitle) can have a direct impact on cognitive load, which may apply to other styles. In the current research lexical errors found in autogenerated subtitles are being examined for their impact on cognitive load. The focus on how subtitles are styled leads directly into the final major area of research, roughly categorised here as subtitle optimisation.

Given that certain subtitle styles are known to cause reading disruption, an open question is how best to optimise subtitles. Most of the research on the production and design of optimised subtitles focuses on reducing cognitive load and achieving high comprehension rates. Factors that have been investigated about optimised subtitle design include things such as the number of lines per subtitle (Szarkowska & Gerber-Morón, 2019), the subtitle speed (Kruger, Wisniewska, & Liao, 2022), or the style of subtitles employed (here verbatim, edited, and standard subtitles) (Szarkowska et al., 2011). This research has generally found that two-line subtitles which match the timing of the dialogue produce the highest level of comprehension according to post-experiment comprehension test results. In terms of subtitling "styles," one example of a style type prominent in the research is integrated subtitles. Integrated subtitles are a style of subtitle where the text is not placed in the bottom third of the screen. They are instead placed closer to the visual focal points in the video (Kruger et al., 2018). Usually this involves moving the dialogue closer to its' speaker and making sure the text does not block anything relevant in the image. Along with this, some integrated subtitles will use subtitle colour and opacity to signal volume or tone. Overall, research on integrated subtitles found that they potentially reduced cognitive load as measured via a decrease in fixation count compared to conventional subtitles (Kruger et al., 2018; Black, 2022). These are some examples of how subtitles can be optimised in how they are designed and presented to viewers, especially in relation to cognitive load management.

2.2 Cognitive Load Theory

Originated by John Sweller, cognitive load theory posits that people's working memory is a limited resource, and this limit influences the amount of information which can be processed at a time (Sweller, 1988). Cognitive load is generally framed as different stimuli's properties requiring different amounts

of cognitive effort to process them. To explain these properties, cognitive load is usually divided into three types (Kruger et al., 2018):

1. **Extraneous load:** The processing load which comes from how information is presented. Extraneous load is composed of elements which increase processing effort but not necessarily comprehension or information retention. Because it is related to presentation, the amount of extraneous load can be manipulated. An example of manipulating extraneous load would be the number of lines subtitles are presented on, as mentioned above (Szarkowska & Gerber-Morón, 2019). Three-line presentation had an increased extraneous load, which resulted in lower comprehension rates.
2. **Intrinsic load:** The processing load associated with the difficulty of information in reference to the prior knowledge of the learner/experiencer. A variety of factors influence the amount of intrinsic load, but they cannot be manipulated directly. For instance, if a person is a trained artist, it will take much less effort for them to learn a new artistic medium than someone completely unexperienced.
3. **Germane load:** The processing load and mental resource allocation for consolidating information into mental schema, associated with overall processing. Mental schemas are thought patterns which organise information based on categories and how they relate to each other. Germane load is the description of the cognitive processes which go into forming these mental schemas. This type of load can be manipulated, primarily through reducing the amount of extraneous load being processed.

While these types of cognitive load are important for understanding how different stimuli impact processing effort, it is important to remember that measures of cognitive load are not able to fully account for individual differences. An example of this is measuring how much processing goes into schema formation because it is largely based on participants' existing knowledge (Doherty & Kruger, 2018). Despite the difficulties individual differences present, it is one of the main theories used to understand how people process stimuli which involve multiple streams of input simultaneously. Cognitive load is usually studied in reference to educational strategies, though it has expanded into other areas of psychological research as well. This is because of the relevance of learning information and seeing how best to present it for the information to be retained. Because cognitive load is entirely internal, it is currently not possible to measure directly. Instead, external realizations are investigated to assess it comparatively, such as comparing eye movement patterns in response to more and less complex stimuli.

2.3 Eye Tracking

One of the main research methods used to analyse cognitive attention is eye tracking. Eye tracking is the process of measuring where people look in a variety of environments/stimulus conditions. One major way this is analysed is using pupil contrast and corneal reflections to track movement, though electric potential of eye-muscles or eye-attached equipment is also used. Eye tracking is used for a variety of research types such as reading studies (Cook & Wei, 2017), reaction time analysis (van Ens et al., 2019), or marketing research (Wedel & Pieters, 2017).

This stems from the strong eye-mind hypothesis which proposes that gaze fixations reflect where people are focusing their attention (Underwood & Everatt, 1992). Eye tracking generally functions by tracking fixations, which are static dwell points, along with saccades, the eye movements between fixation points. Along with these measures, some equipment is able to measure pupillary

contractions or retinal vein tracking, though these are less common (Doherty & Kruger, 2018). Measuring attention through these factors has opened up interesting methodological approaches in multiple disciplines.

One major area within psycholinguistics where eye tracking has been used is in reading studies, which look at eye movement patterns when participants are reading text. Along with generally understanding how gaze movement works during reading, this has been used to investigate a variety of different features such as textual processing speed (Gwizdka, 2014) or how people parse new vocabulary (Godfroid et al., 2017). Even though studies on subtitles are related to reading studies because of the focus on processing textual information, there is competing sensory information not present in most reading studies. Along with this, the addition of other visual and auditory stimuli makes linking them directly to cognitive attention more difficult. Studies on subtitle processing have been increasing in prevalence in recent years, both due to an increase in subtitle availability and eye tracking equipment becoming more efficient and accessible. The latter has been due to increases in available eye tracking technologies, whether it is cheaper desktop setups or software which employ computer webcams (Kok et al., 2023). When looking at subtitles, there are multiple reasons for using eye tracking such as investigating attention, motivation, and cognitive load. Here we will be focusing on cognitive load in regard to the multi-sensory input of subtitled media.

2.4 Measuring Cognitive Load in Eye Tracking

Because of the strong eye-mind hypothesis, eye tracking is able to directly investigate cognitive load responses. One of the primary measures which is linked to cognitive load is pupillary response, with dilation being associated with high cognitive load (Gwizdka, 2014). This is due to decreases in parasympathetic activity in the brain, which impact dilation rates. Because pupillary responses to light level are hard to distinguish from other varieties of responses, this measure is limited to specific stimuli. The variance in light in media such as movies or television shows can interfere with pupillary tracking, even when environmental light levels are consistent. Because of this, subtitle research does not generally employ pupillary response as a factor.

Two other factors often investigated are fixation count and dwell time (also called fixation duration). Higher fixation counts are associated with heightened cognitive load because they imply more information being processed (Kruger, Szarkowska, & Krejtz, 2015). Longer dwell times are also associated with higher cognitive loads, with Holmqvist et al. finding that longer fixations correlate with 'deeper' processing (2011). In the literature deeper processing was not properly defined, but correlates with higher levels of cognitive load, which is how it will be approached here. This more intensive processing type is seen as a way of tracking increases in general cognitive load. Here the factors fixation count and dwell time will be categorized as cognitive measures of study. Some other common factors analysed in eye tracking are based off these, such as area revisits and visit %. Here these will be referred to as behavioural measures because they do not directly track the cognitive processes of viewers, but do measure how they interact with the media they are consuming.

Another way in which attention is analysed in reading studies is saccades/gaze paths, which look at what information is prioritised and in what order (Gwizdka, 2014). Because subtitles are not static, traditional reading study methods which measure saccades between single-word fixations become harder. The difficulty is both due to additional visual input and because viewers have to prioritise certain word types in the limited timeframe (Kruger, Szarkowska, & Krejtz, 2015). In order to account for the dynamic nature of subtitles, Kruger and Steyn developed the Reading Index for Dynamic Texts (RIDT) (2014). This index uses reading study measures of comprehension, including saccades patterns across words, while accounting for the additional visual focus points in subtitled media. The RIDT is calculated

using the number of unique fixations on standard words compared with the average saccade length on that subtitle based on average word length. This index is just one example of the ways research has been adapting to better understand the complex input associated with subtitled media.

The current research will be prioritising fixation count and dwell time as measures of cognitive load because comprehension is not a goal of the current research project. Since they are measures of cognitive load, they are also more responsive to the multimodal nature of subtitled content.

2.5 Multimodal Integration

Multimodal integration is the term for a combination of cognitive processes which simultaneously combine information from separate sensory sources for the brain to process (Kruger et al., 2018). With multiple streams of input, the brain must use collections of inferences and existing schematic connections in order to process. An example of this would be the sensory input received from fireworks. Fireworks produce a brief concussive sound along with bright lights which may be in different shapes or colours. While the concussive sound could be confused with other sources, such as thunder or firearms, the addition of the visual input narrows down the source. Thunder may have an associated bright light in the form of lightning, but this would be a distinctive shape and short duration, while firearms do not have associated light. By processing the multiple sensory input sources using existing schema, comprehenders are able to quickly understand that fireworks are happening near them. In terms of cognitive load theory, multiple sources of input increase the amount of cognitive load, which means people must either miss some of the information or try to adapt their processing behaviours to manage the increased input without becoming overloaded (Kruger et al., 2018).

Within multimodal theories, one of the most relevant components to subtitle processing is the verbal redundancy effect. In multimodality, redundancy is when two input sources are delivery the same information (Kalyuga, 2012). While this often leads to increased cognitive load, this does not seem to hold for verbal redundancy. Verbal redundancy, identical linguistic information produced as multiple separate inputs, is usually discussed in terms of simultaneous signing and speaking. However, another major form is found in subtitles and other read-along texts, which present the information as both written and spoken input. In both of these instances, verbal redundancy has been found to have no increase on cognitive load in comparison to a singular input (Kalyuga, 2012). In fact it has been linked with higher levels of content comprehension, suggesting that the two input streams may in fact reinforce each other, which would aid in schema creation (Kruger, Szarkowska, & Krejtz, 2015). It is believed that this occurs because the multiple streams of linguistic information are in fact the same despite their different forms, which then leads to questions of what happens when it does not align perfectly, such as inaccurate subtitles.

2.6 Multimodal Misalignment

In current research, inaccurate subtitles as a phenomenon are largely unexplored. Some research however has looked at how different subtitle styles impact comprehension and cognitive effort. One such study was conducted by Perego et al. (2010) which tested phrase segmentation in Italian subtitles of a Hungarian television show. They investigated whether viewers responded differently to the separation of an adjective onto a different line from its associated noun. In the end, such adjective-noun separation was not found to have any effect. Other investigations have looked at style of subtitles, such as Orrego-Carmona (2016) and Szarkowska et al. (2011). In the former, professional and amateur translations were compared and no processing difference was found between the two. The latter looked at verbatim, edited, and standard subtitles, with the findings being explained above. While these subtitle

conditions do use subtitles whose content did not fully match what was said or which used a non-standard translation, neither study actually addresses the issue of inaccuracies directly. The lack of research in this area is especially salient with autogenerated subtitles, which are increasingly common and often have lexical inaccuracies. Here lexical inaccuracies are defined as words found in the subtitles which do not have the form as what was spoken in the dialogue. Usually, these inaccuracies occur because of similar phonology being processed by the auto-generation software, leading to the wrong words being output as subtitles. Thus far, these lexical inaccuracies and their impact on viewers' processing of media has been unexplored, so they will be investigated here.

3 Method

3.1 Participants

An availability sample of 29 participants was collected with an average age of 21 ($SD = 1.374$). One participant had to be excluded due to a strong glasses prescription interfering with the eye tracker's ability to find their corneal reflection, so only 28 participants were included in the final data. Participants were collected through convenience sampling using the platform Instagram. The study was advertised as an eye tracking study on subtitles, which would accept any fluent English speakers. The choice to not only investigate native English speakers was made because there is a higher chance non L1 consume media using subtitles, which can't be guaranteed of English L1 speakers in an English-speaking country. The aim of this was to have a participant group better representative of the average subtitle user, thus including both L1 and L2 English speakers. All the participants were students at the University of Edinburgh, Scotland.

64.3% of participants were Native English speakers. Through a classification based on the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) 89.3% of the participants self-reported Advanced-High Proficiency and the remaining 10.7% reported Advanced. Participants were also asked to self-report on if they had any forms of physical or cognitive processing factors which may affect their comprehension of sensory information. While 0% of the participants had any physical factors, 39.3% reported some form of cognitive factors. Due to the limited scope of this study and out of respect for participants' medical privacy, specific details of these factors were not collected. No participants were excluded from any aspect of analysis due to any cognitive processing issues because they represent a large population group known to use intralingual subtitles (Simpson, Dalal, & Senaan, 2022). For the eye-tracking component, all participants reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision. As a part of the post- experiment questionnaire, they were also asked about their usual subtitled media consumption behaviour, but due to confusion expressed by the participants this data will not be considered here. As compensation for their time, participants were offered baked goods provided by the researcher.

3.2 Materials

For the video stimuli, a 10-minute section of the Nat Geo Wild nature documentary Wild Untamed Brazil was selected (see Figure 1). The documentary presents different animal populations which live in the Mata Atlântica forest in coastal Brazil, focusing on the animals' behaviours and the habitats they inhabit. This documentary was selected because of its clear narration, which had a standard RP accent which would be familiar to students in the UK. Along with auditory features familiar to the participants, the entire video is narrated, so no individuals are visibly speaking. This was an important factor so participants would not be able to use any misalignment recovery strategies, such as using lip reading,

facial expressions, or body language (for further discussion on using narrated content, see Kruger, Szarkowska, & Krejtz (2015)).

For the experiment, each participant saw one version of the video: the original un-subtitled video, a version with YouTube auto-generated subtitles (containing lexical errors), and a version with human-corrected subtitles (no errors).

Figure 1: *Original Unmodified Video File: Documentary with no Added Subtitles (Wild Untamed Brazil, 00:00:06).*

For the un-subtitled version, the original video file was left unedited. For the stimulus with subtitle inaccuracies, the auto-generated subtitles were manually corrected so that only lexical errors were present, with a total of 21 lexical errors. For the stimulus with only accurate subtitles, the auto-generated subtitles were manually corrected, making them accurate to the narration. Due to human error, three lexical errors were still present in the third stimulus at the time of the experiment. This was taken into account in the final results, detailed in the analysis plan below.

All subtitles in both stimuli were coded into .srt files, which were then integrated directly into the video files. Due to an error in the file transfer, subtitle #43 was not visible in either stimulus, but since this occurred in both subtitle conditions it did not impact the data analysis plan. The subtitles were integrated into the video using the online service VEED (<https://www.veed.io/>).

Due to cost restrictions, a watermark was visible in the top-left corner of the autogenerated subtitles and the corrected subtitles, but visual inspection confirmed that this was not a common interest area for participants over the 10-minute duration. For maximum visibility throughout the entire video, the subtitles were presented as sans-serif, bold white text. They were also backgrounded by a transparent grey backing for higher visual contrast. The subtitles were placed in the lower third of the screen, so they did not interfere with the focus points of the video and so the subtitle position aligned with the standard subtitles participants are accustomed to (as opposed to another style such as integrated subtitles). Samples of the accurate and inaccurate subtitle versions are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2: *Corrected Subtitles: Documentary with Integrated Human-Corrected Subtitles (Wild Untamed Brazil, 00:00:06).*

Figure 3: *Autogenerated subtitles: Documentary with Lexical Errors Present in the Subtitles (Wild Untamed Brazil, 00:00:06).*

All three stimuli were uploaded into Experiment Builder for presentation to participants during the experiment.

3.3 Procedure

Before being invited to the lab, a copy of the experiment information and consent form were provided to participants to review. After signing the consent forms, the participants were given an anonymized participant number and distributed into one of the three stimulus conditions: The first group (n = 9) was assigned to the stimulus without subtitles, the second (n =9) watched it with embedded autogenerated subtitles including lexical errors, and the third (n =10) watched it with human-corrected subtitles. Before watching the video, participants were informed that they would be completing a demographic and comprehension survey after the video finished. The survey used was a Google Forms questionnaire which was separated into two components. The first component was a series of demographic questions,

the results of which are detailed in the Participants section above. The second component was a series of comprehension questions asking specific content from the video watched during the experiment. These questions related to very specific details from the dialogue of the stimulus, such as “What colour are female Blue Manakins?”

The data collection began with participants being briefed on the eye tracking equipment and stages of the experiment. An important aspect of this was making participants aware that they would be asked comprehension questions after the recording period. Making them aware of the comprehension survey was specifically emphasized to encourage participants to focus on video’s content, which would provide more natural data than if they were consciously primed that the data collection would be about their subtitle attention. The eye tracking system used was an Eyelink 1000 Plus in Tower Mount configuration, using the headmount. The monitor used had a resolution of 1980 x 1020 and was placed 60 centimetres away from the eye tracker. Monocular data was collected from participants’ right eyes. All recording settings were set to the system default and the experiment was designed for the monitor specifications. Throughout all trials a consistent light level was maintained in the room.

The first stage was to calibrate the eye tracker, which was individually done for each participant before the recording began. A 9-point device calibration phase was integrated into the experiment along with a secondary verification stage. Once the calibration was completed, the experimenter began the recording phase. In the recording phase, participants were shown one of the three stimulus videos as the eye tracker recorded their gaze. This data was then recorded as an .edf file. The final phase of the experiment was having participants complete the Google Form which asked them demographic and comprehension questions.

3.4 Analysis Plan

For data analysis, the first thing done was uploading the experiment data files into Data Viewer. Here they were sorted and aggregated by stimulus video. Areas of interest (AOIs) were created for each line of the subtitles, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Autogenerated Subtitle Video Interest Areas, Shown with Fixation Points.

Initially AOIs were also going to be created on the primary visual focus points in each section of the video, but due to time constraints this was deemed beyond the scope of the current project. Because visual focus points were not analysed, data from the un-subtitled group was not used in the final analysis. Additionally, the subtitles which were affected by errors in the design stage were not included in the

analysis in either condition. The data analysed from the interest areas was fixation number, dwell times, trial visit %, and trial runs. Fixation number is the average number of individual fixations which fall inside the AOI. Dwell time is the average time spent on each fixation within the AOI. Trial visit % is the number of participants who had at least one fixation within the AOI, separated by condition. Trial runs, also called revisits, are instances where a fixation occurs inside an AOI followed by one outside and then another inside. These imply that a viewer is focusing on something outside the AOI but returning, which tracks split attention. These are the same measures used in the analysis done by Orrego-Carmona on professional versus non-professional subtitling, as mentioned above (2016).

The analysis targets participants' looking behaviour in the 21 video scenes whose subtitles differ across the accurate and inaccurate versions of the video. The analysis uses averages computed for each scene (computed by averaging across participants), for each of the following four measures: dwell time, fixation number, trial visits, and trial runs. For each measure, a 2-tail paired T-Test was conducted to compare the accurate and inaccurate conditions. In addition, linear regression models were created to examine how participants' behaviour changed throughout the video, using subtitle number as an approximate measure of time. The time analysis was done due to a trend noticed in the data, which prompted further investigation, and provides an opportunity to see whether participants who are exposed to a video with inaccurate subtitles adopt different viewing strategies as the video progresses.

4 Results

Table 1: *Dependent variable statistics*

	Dwell Time (ms)		Fixation Count		Run Count		Visited Trial %	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Corrected		1459.4277	810.5627	332.4028	2.762	1.34	87.5	9.798
Incorrect		1706.819	911.8787	447.3934	2.607	1.4	79.856	11.339

For each of the four dependent variable variables (dwell time, fixation count, run count, and trial visit percent) a 2-Tailed Paired *T*-Test was conducted using the averages of the corrected and inaccurate conditions across the 66 subtitles in the stimuli. All mean and standard deviation values are listed in Table 1 above.

For Dwell Time, inaccurate subtitles yielded longer dwell times than corrected subtitles ($t(131) = 4.0691, p = .0001$). Fixation Count was found to not be significant ($t(131) = 0.5440, p = 0.588326123$). For Run Count, corrected subtitles produced more average runs than inaccurate subtitles ($t(131) = 2.0092, p = 0.0487$). For Visited Trial % inaccurate subtitles yielded lower viewer percentages than corrected subtitles ($t(131) = 5.2548, p = 1.7591E-06$).

Additionally, for all of the dependent variables a linear regression was created with fixed effects for subtitle number (an index of time, included in the model as scaled subtitle number), condition (coded with "corrected" set to -.5 and "incorrect" set to .5) and their interaction. No random effects were included.

The analysis shows that dwell time is lower for correct subtitles and decreases over time (over subsequent subtitle numbers). Both of these main effects are statistically significant (time: $B = -12.254, SE = 3.529, t = -3.472, p < 0.001$; condition: $B = 627.127, SE = 284.482, t = 2.204, p < 0.05$). There is no interaction ($B = -10.911, SE = 7.058, t = -1.546, p = 0.12$).

Figure 5: Dwell time by condition using subtitle number as an approximation of time.

For fixation count the counts decrease significantly over time ($B=-0.04275$, $SE= 0.01671$, $t=-2.558$, $p<0.05$). There is no significant effect of condition nor an interaction ($t < 1$).

Figure 6: Fixation count by condition using subtitle number as an approximation of time.

For run count the counts decrease marginally over time ($B=-0.009864$, $SE= 0.005846$, $t=- 1.687$, $p=0.09$). There is no significant effect of condition nor an interaction ($t < 1$).

Figure 7: Run count by condition using subtitle number as an approximation of time.

For trial visit % the counts decrease significantly over time ($B=-0.09389$, $SE= 0.04444$, $t=-2.113$, $p<0.05$) an effect driven by a marginal interaction ($B=-0.15618$, $SE= 0.08888$, $t=- 1.757$, $p=0.08$), whereby the decrease is more apparent for incorrect subtitles than correct subtitles. There is no significant effect of condition ($t < 1$).

Figure 8: Trial visits % by condition using subtitle number as an approximation of time.

5 Discussion

This experiment aims to explain the cognitive effects of lexical errors in subtitles. By using eye tracking measures, it is possible to look at how multimodal misalignment from verbal stimuli impacts cognitive load. Here we have found that cognitive load is being impacted by inaccurate subtitle conditions, shown through an increase in dwell time. Along with this, participants also alter their viewing behaviours in response to the subtitle accuracy. Additionally, all of the factors investigated showed an effect of time which requires further analysis.

In our discussion of this, we will first discuss each of the eye tracking measures investigated and how these results compare with similar research. The eye tracking measures relating to viewer behaviours will be discussed separately from measures which are theoretically linked directly to cognitive load. We will then discuss the implications of the linear regression models and the need for further analysis of behavioural changes over time in future research.

5.1 Eye Tracking Measures: Fixation Count

In the results, fixation counts were not found to vary by conditions. This is interesting because it differs from the investigation of integrated subtitles by Kruger et al. (2018). Because their research is also on the cognitive load associated with intralingual subtitles, it was expected that similar results would be found. In their research, fixation count was found to be one of the primary significant eye tracking measures, which they linked to extraneous load. What is not clarified in their study is how fixation counts are connected to extraneous load specifically, while dwell time and other factors are measures of average cognitive load at the same time.

Following this idea, the fact that fixation counts are not significant would suggest that additional extraneous load is not impacting the overall cognitive load as would be expected. In this experiment, fixation count did not differ significantly between the conditions, but the differences in other measures suggest that cognitive load is still being impacted. The nonsignificant effect of fixation duration across conditions would imply that lexical errors do not impact the extraneous load, which is interesting because it is the primary form of cognitive load which is known to be manipulated. Some possible reasons for this will be discussed below alongside the other measures.

5.2 Eye Tracking Measures: Dwell Time

Dwell time is taken to indicate average cognitive load and ‘depth’ of processing (Kruger, Szarkowska, & Krejtz, 2015). Even though processing depth is generally an unclear concept within cognitive load theory, it is clear that it has connections to higher overall cognitive load, but not any specific form of it. Generally, the term ‘depth’ seems to suggest that more processing effort is allocated with the assumption that more comprehension would be gained from this, but this is currently not directly stated in any research found. Here dwell time will be discussed in terms of general cognitive load and the potential connections to either intrinsic or germane load.

In the data, dwell time was found to be significantly longer in the inaccurate condition, suggesting that lexical errors do indeed impact cognitive load for viewers. Interestingly, in the same Kruger et al. study mentioned above, dwell time showed no differences by cognitive load even though fixation count did (2018). Because Kruger et al. was investigating integrated subtitles when they found dwell time to have no effect, it is hard to say whether this means that the increased cognitive load is specifically linked with lexical errors, because dwell time has been shown significant in other studies like Szarkowska et al. (2011). Their study included subtitling styles which did not directly match the audio, so their results show that the increase has been found in similar environments elsewhere. The fact that dwell time was significant while fixation count was not could be linked to the fact that fixation count is usually specifically linked with extraneous load, which is a result of the presentation of stimulus information. It also cannot be due to intrinsic load because theoretically it cannot be manipulated because of its relation to the actual informational content of the stimulus. Since it is neither of the other forms of cognitive load, lexical errors may instead be interfering with germane load, which deals with schema formation processes. One possible reason for the impact on germane load could be because lexical errors require viewers to infer what words or concepts were meant to be written, or to process

only the auditory input. At this current stage this is purely speculation and further research will be needed to try and understand this connection.

5.3 Eye Tracking Measures: Visit % and Runs

These two measures are being reported together because neither are typically theoretically linked measures of cognitive load. Instead, they are measures which show the behaviour patterns of viewers under the different conditions. The data showed that both measures differed significantly between the accurate versus inaccurate conditions, with the presence of lexical errors resulting in lower run counts and fewer visits across participants. This suggests that participants are in fact behaving differently under different subtitle conditions. In the case of visit % this means that fewer participants were even reading the subtitles with errors, which suggests that they may not read 'unreliable' subtitles as often. In the case of runs, it is hard to determine because the run count would also be responsive to trial visit %, though it definitely appears that there is a behavioural change. This will be further discussed in the discussion of the behavioural changes over time.

5.4 Viewing Behaviour over Time: Cognitive Measures

The linear regression models are interesting to investigate because time connected analyses are almost unexplored across the literature. Perego et al. (2010) did an analysis of behaviour changes between the first half of a video and the second, but no other studies were found to have any measures of changes across time. Perego et al. reported that in the second half of the video participants increased their fixation counts and dwell time in non-subtitled regions. This does not fully align with the findings here, but because it was an inter-lingual subtitle study it is not surprising that participants responded differently.

In this data, both of the cognitive measures were found to decrease significantly over time. The fact that fixation count decreased over time even though fixation counts didn't differ significantly by subtitle accuracy in the overall data suggests that viewers' processing naturally varies the longer they are exposed to a stimulus. This shows that even under normal subtitled conditions there appears to be a change occurring the longer viewers watch a stimulus. Along with this, dwell time also varied which suggests that the overall cognitive load was varying across time as well. These findings show that more research needs to be done to establish a baseline of how these cognitive measures vary across time.

5.5 Viewing Behaviour over Time: Behavioural Measures

In the analysis of response to subtitle accuracy over time, the behavioural measures also showed a significant change. Additionally, the visit % showed marginal interaction in which the decrease for incorrect subtitles was more apparent than for the corrected condition. This suggests that the lexical errors are causing a difference which is separate from the effect of time alone.

Because this is a measure of how many participants viewed the subtitles, this decrease over time suggests that viewers of inaccurate subtitles are choosing to not process the competing information. If this is true, the misaligned input could be causing people to prioritise the auditory information because it is more accurate. This requires further examination because it is hard to determine how this impacts the accuracy of the other factors.

Because all of the measures were taken from fixations within the AOI, if participants are not reading subtitles as often over time, then the measures from later sections of the video are not accurate. Because of the limited scope of this research, it was not investigated if the same participants tended not to look at inaccurate subtitles or if it is just the average across participants. Future research needs to be

done with an awareness of participants who are not looking at the subtitling region, especially if it is a behaviour chosen by specific individuals. This could be done by an analysis which also looks at these measures on the visual focus points of the videos along with the subtitles. This would show if the cognitive load factors are consistent when prioritising visual, non-textual input.

6 Conclusion

While accurate subtitles are assumed in all subtitles, manual and autogenerated, this is not the reality experienced by viewers. The prevalence of inaccurate subtitles is why it is important that research is not only conscious of this, but actively investigating the effects. Here we have done the initial work by showing that lexical errors both increase cognitive load for viewers and change their viewing behaviour patterns. Establishing a baseline of how viewers respond to lexical errors is a key first step to understanding how people cope with misalignment in co-occurring stimuli. We have also shown that lexical errors do impact viewing behaviours in response to cognitive load as well. While here the data suggests that people may abandon inaccurate stimulus sources as a strategy to cope with misaligned input, this needs to be further investigated. Along with this it is important to see how people utilize other information streams like body language, lip reading, and visual context to recover information. Understanding how multimodal input is integrated and processed will involve further experiments, which could use obstructing different video and audio components to see how different conditions affect cognitive load. This current project has been the first step in understanding how multimodal misalignment affects viewers, which will hopefully help motivate accurate subtitle sources and more awareness of how viewers process information in media.

7 References

- Black, S. (2022). Could integrated subtitles benefit young viewers? Children's reception of standard and integrated subtitles: a mixed methods approach using eye tracking. *Perspectives: Studies in Translation Theory and Practice*, 30(3), 503–519.
- Brahnam, S. (2017). Comparison of in-person and screen-based analysis using communication models: A first step toward the psychoanalysis of telecommunications and its noise. *Psychoanalytic Perspectives*, 14(2), 138-158.
- Cook, A. E., & Wei, W. (2017). Using eye movements to study reading processes: Methodological considerations. In C. Was, F. Sansosti, & B. Morris (Eds), *Eye-tracking technology applications in educational research* (pp. 27-47). Hershey: IGI Global.
- Doherty, S., & Kruger, J. L. (2018). The development of eye tracking in empirical research on subtitling and captioning. In T. Dwyer, C. Perkins, S. Redmond & J. Sita (Eds), *Seeing into screens: Eye tracking and the moving image* (pp. 46-64). London: Bloomsbury.
- van Ens, W., Schmidt, U., Campbell, I. C., Roefs, A., & Werthmann, J. (2019). Test-retest reliability of attention bias for food: Robust eye-tracking and reaction time indices. *Appetite*, 136, 86-92.
- Godfroid, A., Ahn, J., Choi, I. N. A., Ballard, L., Cui, Y., Johnston, S., ... & Yoon, H. J. (2018). Incidental vocabulary learning in a natural reading context: An eye-tracking study. *Bilingualism: Language and Cognition*, 21(3), 563-584.
- Goldman, M., & Goldman, S. (1988). Reading with close-captioned TV. *Journal of Reading*, 31(5), 458-461.
- Gwizdka, J. (2014, August). Characterizing relevance with eye-tracking measures. *Proceedings of the 5th information interaction in context symposium*, 58-67.

- Holmqvist, K., Nyström, M., Andersson, R., Dewhurst, R., Jarodzka, H., & Van de Weijer, J. (2011). *Eye tracking: A comprehensive guide to methods and measures*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kalyuga, S. (2012). Instructional benefits of spoken words: A review of cognitive load factors. *Educational Research Review*, 7(2), 145-159.
- Kok, E. M., Jarodzka, H., Sibbald, M., & van Gog, T. (2023). Did You Get That? Predicting Learners' Comprehension of a Video Lecture from Visualizations of Their Gaze Data. *Cognitive Science*, 47(2), e13247.
- Kruger, J. (2013). Subtitles in the classroom: Balancing the benefits of dual coding with the cost of increased cognitive load. *Journal for Language Teaching*, 47(1), 29-53.
- Kruger, J. L., Doherty, S., Fox, W., & de Lissa, P. (2018). Multimodal measurement of cognitive load during subtitle processing: Same-language subtitles for foreign-language viewers. *Innovation and expansion in translation process research*, 18, 267-294.
- Kruger, J. L., & Steyn, F. (2014). Subtitles and eye tracking: Reading and performance. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 49(1), 105–120.
- Kruger, J. L., Szarkowska, A., & Krejtz, I. (2015). Subtitles on the moving image: An overview of eye tracking studies. *Refractory: a journal of entertainment media*, 25, 1-14.
- Kruger, J. L., Wisniewska, N., & Liao, S. (2022). Why subtitle speed matters: Evidence from word skipping and rereading. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 43(1), 211–236.
- Liao, S., Kruger, J. L., & Doherty, S. (2020). The impact of monolingual and bilingual subtitles on visual attention, cognitive load, and comprehension. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, 33, 70-98.
- Nat Geo Wild. (2014). *Wild Untamed Brazil* [Video].
<https://www.natgeotv.com/za/shows/nationalgeographicwild/wild-untamed-brazil>.
- Orrego-Carmona, D. (2016). A reception study on non-professional subtitling: Do audiences notice any difference? *Across Languages and Cultures*, 17(2), 163–181.
- Perego, E., del Missier, F., Porta, M., & Mosconi, M. (2010). The cognitive effectiveness of subtitle processing. *Media Psychology*, 13(3), 243–272.
- Simpson, E., Dalal, S., & Semaan, B. (2022). "Hey, Can You Add Captions?": The Critical Infrastructuring Practices of Neurodiverse People on TikTok. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.06204*, 1-27.
- Sun, K., & Wang, R. (2019). Frequency distributions of punctuation marks in English: Evidence from large-scale corpora. *English Today*, 35(4), 23-35.
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257-285.
- Szarkowska, A., & Gerber-Morón, O. (2019). Two or three lines: a mixed-methods study on subtitle processing and preferences. *Perspectives: Studies in Translation Theory and Practice*, 27(1), 144–164.
- Szarkowska, A., Krejtz, I., Klyszejko, Z., & Wiczorek, A. (2011). Verbatim, standard, or edited? reading patterns of different captioning styles among deaf, hard of hearing, and hearing viewers. *American Annals of the Deaf*, 156(4).
- Underwood, G., & Everatt, J. (1992). The role of eye movements in reading: Some limitations of the eye-mind assumption. *Advances in psychology*, 88, 111-169.
- Veed - Online. VEED.IO. (n.d.). Retrieved February 25, 2023, from <https://www.veed.io/>.
- Wedel, M., & Pieters, R. (2017). A review of eye-tracking research in marketing. *Review of marketing research*, 123-147.

Yoon, J. O., & Kim, M. (2011). The effects of captions on deaf students' content comprehension, cognitive load, and motivation in online learning. *American Annals of the Deaf*, 156(3), 283-289.

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